

DETERMINANTS OF LECTURER PERFORMANCE: INTEGRATING KNOWLEDGE, MOTIVATION, SUSTAINABILITY AND COMMITMENT THROUGH A JOB SATISFACTION PERSPECTIVE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17151288>

Keywords

Knowledge management, organizational commitment, work motivation, sustainability practices, lecturer performance, job satisfaction, higher education

Article History

Received: 11 June 2025

Accepted: 03 September 2025

Published: 18 September 2025

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Abstract

In today's increasingly competitive, knowledge-driven academic environment, the lecturers' performance is a critical determinant of institutional quality, reputation, and long-term sustainability. However, superior performance extends beyond individual capabilities, requiring the interplay of multiple organizational and personal factors. The study investigates how knowledge, organizational commitment, work motivation, and suitability practices collectively shape lecture performance. Job satisfaction is conceptualized as a key mediating factor that strengthens lecturer performance. Grounded on social exchange theory, thirteen hypotheses were developed and empirically tested within an integrated model using a cross-sectional survey of academic staff. SmartPLS 4 was employed to validate the integrated model for the measurement model and hypothesis testing. The findings are expected to advance theoretical understanding by revealing how human, rational, and institutional resources collectively drive lecture performance. Moreover, the study offers practical implications for higher education leaders, particularly in designing policies and interventions, such as effective KM systems, commitment-building HR practices, motivational strategies, and sustainability initiatives that foster academic staff performance and strengthen institutional outcomes.

Introduction

Higher educational institutions (HEIs) have become pivotal engines of innovation, social progress, and sustainable development within today's knowledge-driven economy (AlQhtani, 2025). At the core of higher education institutions, lectures play a pivotal role in disseminating knowledge, shaping future leaders, fostering critical thinking, and driving institutional excellence (ZhengKang et al., 2025). As global competition for talent and innovation

intensifies, academic staff performance emerges as a key determinant of institutional reputation and societal contribution (AlQhtani, 2025; Bu et al., 2025). However, the importance of the mechanisms through which various organizational and human resources practices shape lecturer performance remains fragmented in existing understanding, offering fragmented insights rather than a coherent, theory-driven

perspective (Håkansson & Johansson, 2025; Mentini, 2024)

A central strategic capability in enhancing knowledge management performance encompasses creating, storing, sharing, and applying organizational knowledge (Abbas & Khan, 2023; Migdadi, 2022). A robust knowledge management system provides lecturers access to intellectual resources, pedagogical tools, and collaborative networks that enrich teaching effectiveness, research productivity, and curriculum innovation (Ibarra-Cisneros et al., 2023). In the absence of an effective knowledge management system, knowledge often remains siloed, reducing cross-disciplinary collaboration and constraining institutional learning opportunities (Muller, 2025; Suija-Markova, 2022). Although the significance of knowledge management is widely acknowledged, empirical investigation into direct pathways to lecturer performance, especially within developing and resource-constrained educational contexts, is limited, specifically in the Pakistani context.

Beyond knowledge resources, organizational commitment is also defined as employees' psychological attachment and loyalty to their organization, and has been identified as a critical driver of organizational performance (Patwary et al., 2025; Purwanto, 2020). Committed lecturers are more likely to demonstrate greater willingness to exceed contractual obligations, align with institutional goals, and endure professional challenges (Anvari et al., 2023). Furthermore, organizational commitment fosters team stability within academic teams, enabling long-term collaboration and program development (ZhengKang et al., 2025). Nevertheless, in many higher education settings, increasing administrative burdens, performance pressures, and resource constraints threaten to erode commitment levels, making it imperative to understand how commitment interacts with other factors to sustain high performance (Patwary et al., 2025).

Another key determinant is work motivation, which reflects the internal driver and sustained efforts employees invest in their professional roles (Aljumah, 2023; Ned & Umesi, 2023). Motivated

lecturers engage more deeply in lesson preparation, student interaction, research, and professional development (Aljumah, 2023; Chadha, 2024). Drawing on self-determination theory, intrinsic motivation, nurtured by autonomy, mastery, and pursuit, is particularly vital in academic work, where creativity and long-term engagement are required for a sustainable ecosystem (Guo Nyuhuan, 2024). However, motivation can be undermined by institutional policies that fail to recognize individual contribution or provide opportunities for growth, highlighting the importance of organizational strategies that nurture and sustain motivation over time.

Combining these human-capital factors, knowledge management, and work motivation, embody an institution's commitment to environmental stewardship, social responsibility, and ethical governance (Alemu & Burrell, 2025; Aljumah, 2023). Within HEIs, sustainability practices, including green campus initiatives, community outreach programs, and socially responsible research, enhance institutional reputation and create a meaningful work environment, not only enhancing institutional reputation (Hammami & Othmani, 2024) but also aligning with lecturer values, reinforcing job satisfaction and meaningful engagement (Baah et al., 2021). Job satisfaction is widely recognized as a predictor of performance, as satisfied employees tend to demonstrate higher engagement, creativity, and organizational citizenship behaviours (Ansong et al., 2024; Meynhardt et al., 2020). As a mediator, job satisfaction is an explanatory pathway for understanding how organizational resources are translated into tangible performance outcomes (Zang et al., 2022). However, empirical testing of job satisfaction as a mediator in integrated performance models remains rare in higher education research, particularly in emerging economies like Pakistan.

In the Pakistani higher education sector, lecturers' performances are increasingly shaped by systemic gaps where institutional policies fail to align with individual capabilities. Many universities adopt fragmented approaches,

addressing knowledge management, organizational commitment, and work motivation separately rather than integrally. Such disjointed strategies undermine lecturers' performances, as these overlook the interplay of organizational and individual factors. Existing studies often examine predictors like knowledge management and organizational commitment in isolation, neglecting their combined effects on performance. However, the global evidence highlights job satisfaction as a decisive driver of performance; in Pakistan, the potential impact of job satisfaction as a mediator remains unexplored. As a result, universities risk relying on short-term fixes rather than integrated, evidence-based strategies that strengthen knowledge flows, foster commitment, sustain motivation, and embed sustainability into everyday academic practices. This is particularly critical in a context with limited resources, heavy teaching loads, high faculty turnover, and rising demands for quality improvement. Without a coordinated effort to address these interconnected factors, the performance gap will likely persist, constraining institutional competitiveness and lecturers' professional growth.

Against this backdrop, the primary objective of this study is to examine how knowledge management, organizational commitment, work motivation, and sustainability practices collectively and interactively influence lecturer performance in Pakistan's higher education sector, with job satisfaction serving as a mediating mechanism. By integrating these dimensions into an unified framework, the study seeks to uncover the synergistic effects often overlooked in isolated investigations. Specifically, it examines the extent to which effective knowledge sharing and utilization, a strong sense of institutional commitment, intrinsic work motivation, and embedded sustainability practices contribute to enhancing job satisfaction, and how, in turn, this satisfaction drives superior lecturer performances. This approach intends to provide empirical insights to guide universities in designing holistic, evidence-based strategies to address performance challenges in resource-constrained environments,

reduce faculty turnover, and improve academic quality aligned with national and global educational priorities.

Literature Reviews

Development of Hypotheses Grounded on Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory (SET) offers a powerful lens for understanding organizational dynamics in higher education (Sulistyan, 2020). Rooted in Blau's (1964) foundational work and later refined by Purwanto (2020), SET posits that workplace relationships are sustained through reciprocal exchanges of both tangible and intangible resources, with actors motivated to reciprocate benefits received (Arsawan et al., 2020). Applied to higher education institutions, this implies that when universities provide valuable resources and support structures, lecturers will likely reciprocate through enhanced effort, loyalty, and performance (Abdou et al., 2022). The study leverages SET as it aptly explains how institutional factors (knowledge management and sustainability practices) (Thomas & Gupta, 2021) and individual factors (organizational commitment and work motivation) (Abdou et al., 2022) shape job satisfaction, which in turn drives lecturer performance (Zeb et al., 2023). Prior studies of Meynhardt et al. (2020); Aljumah, (2023), and Baah et al. (2021) have examined these constructs largely in isolation. Few studies have integrated, within a reciprocal exchange framework, how and why these factors influence performance in higher education, particularly in resource-constrained contexts like Pakistan. This study addresses these gaps by grounding the conceptual model in SET and offering a more holistic and causally coherent model of lecturer performance.

Knowledge Management (KM)

Knowledge management (KM) in higher education is widely regarded as a strategic resource that enhances organizational learning, innovation, and institutional performance (Muller, 2025). In higher education, Abbas & Khan (2023) indicated that KM practices involve acquiring, sharing, and applying academic

knowledge, enabling lecturers to refine pedagogical methods, update curriculum, and engage in collaborative research (Ibarra-Cisneros et al., 2023). Recent studies of (Abbas & Khan, 2023; Migdadi, 2022) demonstrated that universities with an effective KM system foster environments that support teaching innovation and effectiveness, thereby positively influencing lecturer performance (Muller, 2025).

Despite this evidence, universities in Pakistan often struggle with a fragmented knowledge-sharing culture, weak digital infrastructure, and resistance to adopting KM practices (Abbas & Khan, 2023). While research in Western contexts establishes KM as a performance driver, few studies have integrated KM with psychological mediating factors such as job satisfaction (Migdadi, 2022). Consequently, the gap limits understanding of the mechanisms through which KM translates into lecturer performance outcomes. This perspective addresses a pressing issue in Pakistani higher education: the underutilization of knowledge resources and the lack of systemic processes to translate them into tangible performance outcomes.

Organizational Commitment (OC)

Organizational commitment refers to employees' psychological attachment, identification, and loyalty to their institution and is a well-established predictor of persistence, discretionary effort, and resilience (Patwary et al., 2025; Purwanto, 2020). In academia, committed lecturers are more likely to persevere, be willing to engage in extra-role behavior, and be resilient in facing constraints. A comprehensive meta-analysis of Khan (2024) confirms a robust positive relationship between OC and lecturer performances across heterogeneous settings, suggesting influence in generalizable even within a resource-constrained higher education system (Patwary et al., 2025). However, empirical evidence from Kang et al. (2025), indicates that commitment levels among Pakistani lecturers remain inconsistent, often due to contractual employment structures, limited growth opportunities, and weak institutional support.

Unlike Western universities (Purwanti et al., 2024; Purwanto, 2020), many Pakistani HEIs struggle to create an environment that often fails to provide a conducive environment, reinforcing loyalty (Yousaf et al., 2020). This contextual divergence underscores the necessity of empirically testing OC within the Pakistani academic landscape (Yousaf et al., 2020). The present study adds value by framing OC as a determinant of job satisfaction, which in turn mediates and enhances lecturers' performance. This approach emotionally attaches and coordinates performance outcomes, which is neglected mainly from a South Asian perspective.

Work Motivation (WM)

Work motivation is a critical determinant of job satisfaction and employee performance (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Motivated lecturers engaged in innovative teaching methods, research productivity, and student mentorship (Bice et al., 2022). Self-motivation determination theory distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic motivators, significantly influencing academic staff outcomes (Zeb et al., 2023). Recent findings of (Bice et al., 2022; Zeb et al., 2023) confirm that motivated lecturers report a high satisfaction level, contributing to improved teaching effectiveness and institutional reputation. In Pakistan, Rafiq et al. (2023) argued that structural challenges often undermine lecturers' motivations, including inadequate pay, resource constraints, and limited recognition. This demotivated climate exacerbates job dissatisfaction and weakens performance (Gideon, 2023). While international lecturers extensively documented the motivation-performance link as a mediator, the link between job satisfaction remains unexplored. In the Pakistani context, this study bridges the gap by empirically investigating how work motivation fosters lecturers' satisfaction and subsequently enhances performance. This model provides insight into how intrinsic and extrinsic drivers can be leveraged by university management to cultivate both satisfaction and performance, making it contextually valuable for Pakistan's higher education system.

Sustainability Practices (SP)

Sustainability practices in higher education encompass eco-friendly operations, social responsibility, and ethical academic awareness (Amini et al., 2024). Recent scholarships (Amini et al., 2024; Sepetis et al., 2020) highlight their significance in shaping organizational climate that influences lecturers' attitude and performance by embedding sustainability into teaching, research, and operations (Begum et al., 2021). The university cultivates a sense of purpose and belonging among faculty members, strengthening your job satisfaction and commitment to the organization (Begum et al., 2021; Nagar, 2012). Previous studies of Amini et al. (2024); Begum et al. (2021) and Sepetis et al. (2020) primarily focus on students' perception of sustainability with limited attention to how such practices influence the lectures' performance; consequently, that's like psychological impact of sustainability adoption on faculty satisfaction and profanity remains unexplored from a Pakistani perspective. The current study addresses and innovates by positioning sustainability practices as a strategic HR, to job satisfaction and lecturer performances, highlighting sustainability as an overlooked but valuable lever for academic excellence.

Job Satisfaction (JS)

Job satisfaction, defined as employees' positive evaluation of their work experience, is a key mediator between institutional practices and performance outcomes (Khan et al., 2019). Satisfied lecturers demonstrated higher commitment, motivation, and innovative teaching practices (Roslaeni et al., 2025). Multiple studies of Al-Abdullat & Dababneh (2018); Hendri (2019), and Khan et al. (2019) also confirm that job satisfaction mediates the performance outcome, which ultimately affects the lecturer's performance. In Pakistan, Khan et al. (2019) indicated that resource shortages, heavy teaching load, and inadequate recognition often compromise lecturers' job satisfaction. At the same time, international scholars such as Al-Abdullat & Dababneh, (2018) recognized job

satisfaction as a mediator of the lecture performance. Therefore, this study innovates by placing job satisfaction as a central mediating construct, explaining how institutional practice translates into lecture performance. This refined conceptualization is particularly centralized in Pakistan's higher education sectors, where lecturers' dissatisfaction threatens teaching quality and student learning outcomes.

Lecturer Performance (LP)

Lecturer's performance is a multidimensional construct encompassing teaching effectiveness, research productivity, community engagement, and administrative distributions (Al-Dmour et al., 2025). Studies of Roslaeni et al. (2025) suggested that supportive institutional, job satisfaction, and personal motivation are vital to lecturers' performance. However, in Pakistan, scholars such as Habib et al. (2021); Iqbal et al. (2019) and Rafiq et al. (2023) have raised concerns about declining performance in higher education institutes, which have been revised with criticism pointing to inadequate HR practices, poor knowledge management, and a lack of sustainability orientations. Despite the essentiality of lecturer performance, primarily measured in research output, it neglects the broader teaching from a Pakistani perspective (Rafiq et al., 2023). By integrating diverse antecedents mediated through job satisfaction, this study proposes a holistic approach that addresses past research's fragmented approaches and responds directly to Pakistan's systemic challenges in higher education.

Critical Analysis and Contribution

This study identifies critical gaps and introduces distinct novelty, with existing research solely examining how knowledge management, organizational commitment, work motivation, and sustainability practices primarily originate from developed economies, limiting the applicability to South Asian Contexts, particularly in Pakistan. Furthermore, prior studies often neglect the mediating role of job satisfaction, leaving the mechanisms linking

institutional practices to lecturer performances. Lecturer performances have also been narrowly conceptualized, focusing mainly on research productivity while overlooking teaching, mentoring, and community engagement. The novelty of this study lies in proposing an integrative framework that positions job satisfaction as a central mediator, contextualizing findings within Pakistan's systemic higher education challenges, and advancing both theoretical and practical understanding. This contribution offers administrators actionable pathways to strengthen lecturer performances through holistic institutional strategies.

List of Hypotheses of the Study

- H1: Knowledge management has a positive impact on university lecturer performance.
- H2: Organizational commitment positively affects university lecturer performance.
- H3: Work motivation positively affects lecturer performance among university lecturers.
- H4: Sustainability practices positively affect lecturer performance among university lecturers.

- H5: Job satisfaction positively affects lecturer performance among university lecturers.
- H6: Knowledge management positively affects job satisfaction among university lecturers.
- H7: Organizational commitment positively affects job satisfaction among university lecturers.
- H8: Work motivation positively affects job satisfaction among university lecturers.
- H9: Sustainability practices positively affect job satisfaction among university lecturers.
- H1a: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between Knowledge management and lecturers' performance.
- H2b: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between Organizational commitment and lecturers' performance.
- H3c: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between Work motivation and lecturers' performance.
- H4d: Job satisfaction mediates the relationship between Sustainability practices and lecturers' performance

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Research Methodology

This research adopted A quantitative cross-sectional design to empirically test the proposed relationship between knowledge management organizational commitment work motivation sustainability practice job satisfaction and letter to lecture performance a service based approach is one considered the most appropriate method to capture the perception of lectures working in higher education student across Pakistan given the complexity of the model and the inclusion of mediating path the quantitative design allow for the systematic collaborate collection analyze the data to test the hypothesis with the static statistically rigor.

The population of the study comprise comprised lectured employee in ten (public and private) universities in Pakistan to ensure the representative and reduce the professional sampling bias are stratified technique was employed university was certified in the public and private sectors and proportionally sampling world drawn from each this approach provide a balance representation across different institutional types and help capture the diversity of experience among the Pakistan lectures a total of 371 valid responses were collected a sample such that meet the requirement for partial model equation was recommended by higher at all 2029 this number not only satisfied the ten time rules but also exceed the threshold required to achieve the sufficient statistical power for detecting structure relationship.

For the reliability of the proposed model constructs, Knowledge management using items adopted from Abbas & Khan (2023) and Migdadi (2022), with modifications to suit higher education. Organization commitment items were selected from Patwary et al. (2025) and Purwanto (2020). Sustainability practices were assessed using items from Begum et al. (2021) and Nagar, (2012). Job satisfaction items were selected from Al-Abdullat & Dababneh, (2018); Hendri, (2019) and Khan et al. (2019). While lecture performance was assessed through indicating adopting from Iqbal et al. (2019) and Rafiq et al. (2023) which covered teaching effectiveness research, involvement and mentoring the

contribution all item of our on a 5 point Likert scales (ranging from 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree) presenting small group of lecture to ensure the clarity and contextual appropriations and the face validity of the instrument. A total of 24 items were adopted to evaluate the proposed mediation model.

For data analysis, this study employed SmartPLS 4, a variance-based structural equation model software widely used for predictive research and the model development process. Several methodologies and strategies guided the choice of SmartPLS 4. First, it is well-suited for analyzing complex models with multiple constructs with mediating pathways. Secondly, SmartPLS 4 is a prediction-oriented approach that aligns with the objective of the studies, which is the development of exploratory insight into lecture performance. Third, SmartPLS 4 efficiently collects survey data from heterogeneous populations, ensuring robust and generalizable findings. Collectively, these features make SmartPLS 4 an appropriate and effective tool for testing the proposed research model within the context of higher education.

The analysis followed a stages approach consisting of the measurement model and structure model, indicators reliability was first assessed by examining the factor loading, ensuring that each item achieved the minimum threshold value of 0.708, internal consistency was confirmed through composite reliability, threshold value of 0.700 confirming validity power assessed using average various extractions with the minimum threshold value 0.500, considering acceptable and reliable. Discriminate validity was further established as constructs work empirically distinct from one another. After the measurement model was validated, the structural model was examined. The first step of the structure model is full collinearity testing, through which evaluating the various inflation factors with a minimum threshold of 5 indicates the absence of multicollinearity among the multiple narratives. The path coefficient was tested at 5% confidence level, using a bootstrapping procedure with 1000 resamples to determine the relative contribution of each predictor. Finally, a mandating analysis was

performed to test the indirect effects of knowledge management, organizational commitment, work motivation, and sustainability practices on lecturer performances through job satisfaction.

Demographical Profile of Respondents

The demographical profile of respondents presented in Table 1 reflected a well-balanced representation of participants drawn from ten (public and private) universities in the Punjab region, Pakistan, thereby ensuring the diversity and inclusiveness of the sample. A total of 370 valid responses were collected and distributed across ten universities. Among them, Superior University contributed the highest proportion (21.1%), followed closely by the National College of Business Administration & Economics (11.9%) and University of Central Punjab (10.8%). The COMSATS and the University of Lahore represented 10% of the sample. Meanwhile, Gift University and the FAST accounted for 9.4% each. LUMS contributed 9.7%, SZABIST 8.6%, and the University of Management Technology 8.1%. This contribution highlights that no single intuition dominates the sample, which supports the

representativeness and generalizability of the findings within the regional context.

Regarding gender, male respondents constituted a large proportion of the sample, representing 59.3% (n =220), while female respondents comprised 40.7% (n=151). This indicated that male perspectives are strongly represented in the study, reflecting the increasing engagement of male students in higher education. Regarding educational background, the majority of respondents held a master's degree with 18 years of education (45.9%), followed by those with a master's degree of 16 years (32.3%), and PhD candidates represented 21.8% of the sample, ensuring that the study benefits from insights across different academic levels. Regarding the experiences, the largest segment of respondents had between 1 and 5 years of experience (37.6%), followed by those with 6-10 years (29.7%). A smaller proportion reported 11-15 years of experience (18.8%), and only 13.8% had more than 16 years of experience. This distribution suggests that most respondents are relatively early in their professional careers. The results of the demography are represented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographical Profile of Respondents

University	Respondents	%
University of Lahore	37	10.0
Gift University	35	9.4
University management technology	30	8.1
University of Central Punjab	40	10.8
Commission on Science and Technology for Sustainable Development in the South	37	10.0
Superior University	45	12.1
Foundation for Advancement of Science and Technology	35	9.4
Shaheed Zulfikar Ali Bhutto Institute of Science and Technology	32	8.6
National College of Business Administration & Economics	44	11.9
Lahore university of management sciences	36	9.7
Gender		
Males	220	59.3
Female	151	40.7
Education level		
Master's 16 years	120	32.3
Master's 18 years	170	45.9

PhD	81	21.8
Experiences (Years)		
1 - 5	140	37.6
6 - 10	110	29.7
11 - 15	70	18.8
16+	51	13.8

After the demographic analysis, the next stage of analysis involves evaluating the measurement model, which forms the foundation of the study's structural equation modeling approach. For this purpose, SmartPLS 4 was employed, a highly versatile tool in business and social research. The software is widely recognized for its ability to handle complex models with multiple constructs and indicators, particularly in exploratory studies or when data do not meet the stringent requirements of covariance-based SEM (Hair et al., 2021). Its graphical interface and advanced features, including bootstrapping and predictive power assessments, make it particularly suitable for evaluating latent constructs and lecturer performances in this study. Moreover, SmartPLS 4 ensures flexibility in handling non-normal data and small to medium sample sizes, which fits the current research design involving 371 respondents from ten universities in the Punjab region, Pakistan.

Measurement Model

The measurement model, also referred to as the outer model, was assessed to ensure that the reliability and validity of the constructs were established. Following the guidelines of Hair et al. (2021), several statistical indicators were applied, such as indicator reliability, which was

established by examining factor loading, where values above 0.708 were considered satisfactory, and loading above 0.400 were acceptable if supported by a strong average variance extracted (AVE) greater than 0.500. Internal consistency reliability was confirmed through composite reliability, which should exceed 0.700. In addition, convergent validity was established when the AVE for each construct exceeded the threshold of 0.500, indicating that the latent construct explained more than half of the variance in the indicators.

The results mentioned in Table 2 revealed strong performances across all constructs. Factors loading ranged from 0.583 to 0.854, demonstrating adequate to strong indicator reliability. Composite reliability values fell between 0.809 and 0.873, all surpassing the recommended threshold, ensuring above the 0.500 cut-off, thus confirming convergent validity. These results establish the robustness of the measurement model and provide a strong basis for proceeding to evaluate the structural model. The detailed results are presented in Table 2, which outlines the factor loading, composite reliability, and AVE values for each construct, making it valid and reliable for exploring the relationship among the constructs.

Table 2: Model Measurement

Variable		Loading	AVE	CR
Job Satisfaction	Job satisfaction influences the performance and effectiveness of lecturers in higher education institutions.	0.791	0.514	0.793
	Organizational commitment and motivation play a role in shaping job satisfaction among academic staff.	0.793		
	Knowledge management practices contribute to enhancing job satisfaction among lecturers.	0.573		

	Sustainability-oriented practices within universities impact lecturer job satisfaction and overall institutional outcomes.	0.689		
Knowledge Management	The knowledge management influences lecturers' job satisfaction.	0.747	0.616	0.817
	Knowledge sharing among academic staff fosters innovation, and collaboration with higher education enhances lecturer performance.	0.786		
	The rich knowledge resources support the lecturer's teaching quality and research productivity.	0.770		
	I believe a knowledge management system strengthens organizational commitment and motivates the university faculty.	0.835		
Lecturer Performance	Job satisfaction enhances lecturers' ability to achieve high-quality teaching and institutional performance.	0.669	0.540	0.720
	I believe organizational commitment fosters resilience, dedication, and excellence in lecturer performance.	0.752		
	I believe a positive working intention influences lecturers' engagement, productivity, and performance in HEIs.	0.747		
	I believe that effective knowledge management practices strengthen lecturers' teaching innovation, research contribution, and academic performance.	0.768		
Organizational Commitment	I believe organizational commitment enhances lecturers' sense of belonging and engagement within higher education institutions.	0.720	0.631	0.807
	I believe organizational commitment strengthens job satisfaction and motivation to perform effectively.	0.836		
	I believe organizational commitment contributes to improved teaching quality and lecturer performance.	0.848		
	I believe, organizational commitment serves as a driving force for sustaining institutional effectiveness and academic excellence.	0.766		
Sustainability Practices	I am sure that sustainability practices in higher education institutions enhance lecturers' commitment to teaching and excellence.	0.797	0.586	0.780
	I believe that sustainability initiatives improve lecturers' job satisfaction and overall well-being.	0.861		
	I believe sustainability practices support lecturers' long-term effectiveness and performance within universities.	0.743		
	I believe that sustainability-driven policies foster innovation, motivation, and resiliency among	0.645		

	academic staff.		
Work Motivation	I believe work motivation influences lecturer effectiveness in teaching and community engagement.	0.520	0.720
	I believe intrinsic motivation enhances a lecturer's commitment to achieving academic excellence.	0.676	
	I believe motivational strategies adopted by universities strengthen lecturers' job satisfaction and performance.	0.822	
	I believe that work motivation contributes to sustaining long-term lecturer performance and institutional success.	0.716	0.657

Discriminant validity was assessed using the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio, following the guidelines of Henseler et al. (2015), which suggest values should remain between 0.580 to confirm constructs are distinct. As shown in Table 3, all HTMT values across the constructs were comfortably below the recommended threshold values. This demonstrates that each

construct is empirically distinct, complementary to problematic, overlaps, and appropriately measured. The confirmation of discriminant validity strengthens the reliability of the measurement model and ensures the robustness of subsequent structural model analysis (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

	Job Satisfaction	Knowledge Management	Lecturer Performance	Organizational Commitment	Sustainability Practices	Work Motivation
Job Satisfaction						
Knowledge Management	0.558					
Lecturer Performance	0.720	0.559				
Organizational Commitment	0.451	0.703	0.729			
Sustainability Practices	0.537	0.587	0.578	0.674		
Work Motivation	0.560	0.480	0.451	0.608	0.555	

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Assessment of Structural Model

Following the measurement model, the next step is the evaluation of the structural model to examine the hypothesized relationship between constructs at the 5% significance level among the constructs. Evaluating the structural model followed Hair et al. (2021), focusing on inner model evaluation, for the first step, including inner model, inner collinearity, the coefficient of determination, and path coefficients. The structural model assessment commenced with collinearity diagnostics to ensure the

accuracy of the model estimate. In line with Hair et al. (2021), VIF values below the recommended threshold of 5 suggest that multicollinearity is not a concern. As shown in Table 4, all predictor relationships demonstrated VIF values ranging from 1.460 to 4.329, confirming their acceptability. The lowest VIF was observed for Job satisfaction, indicating minimal collinearity risk in the path. Collectively, these results confirm that the model is free from harmful collinearity issues, thereby reinforcing the robustness and stability of the structural model for subsequent hypothesis testing and interpretation.

Table 4: Collinearity Diagnostics

Relationships	VIF
Job Satisfaction → Lecturer Performance	1.460
Knowledge Management → Job Satisfaction	2.328
Knowledge Management → Lecturer Performance	2.484
Organizational Commitment → Job Satisfaction	2.961
Organizational commitment → Lecturer Performance	2.985
Sustainability Practices → Job Satisfaction	2.575

Sustainability Practices → Lecturer Performance	2.581
Work Motivation → Job Satisfaction	3.311
Work Motivation → Lecturer Performance	3.329

Following the collinearity assessment, the structural model was further evaluated to determine its predictive power using the coefficient of determination. This measure, which ranges from 0 to 1, reflects the proportion of variance in an endogenous construct that can be explained by respective exogenous predictors (Hair et al., 2021). As reported in Table 5, the R-square value of job satisfaction was 0.515, indicating that knowledge management, organizational commitment, suitability practices, and work motivation collectively account for 51.5% of the variance. Similarly, lecture

performances yielded an R-square of 0.697, suggesting that job satisfaction and the direct effects of knowledge management, organizational commitment, sustainability practices, and work motivation explain approximately 70% of the variance. These findings highlight that nearly half of the variance in job satisfaction and more than two-thirds of the variance in lecturer performances are captured by the model, reflecting moderate to substantial explanatory power, while the remaining unexplained variance indicates opportunities for future research to incorporate additional predictors.

Table 5: Coefficient of Determination

	R-square
Job Satisfaction	0.515
Lecturer Performance	0.697

Assessment of Path Coefficient

The structural model assessment proceeded with the evaluation of path coefficients to test the hypothesized relationship among the constructs. Using a one-tailed bootstrapping procedure with 1000 resamples in PLS-SEM 4, the hypotheses were examined at a 5% significance level, in line with Hair et al. (2021). A t-value exceeding the threshold of 1.645 was considered statistically significant, while effect sizes were also calculated to assess each exogenous construct's substantive contribution, following the guidelines of Cohen (1988). The effect sizes were computed to determine the magnitude of influence exerted by

exogenous constructs on the endogenous variables. The F-square metric indicates practical significance, complementing statistical significance (Sullivan et al., 2012). Following Cohen (1988), effect sizes were classified as small (0.02), medium (0.15), and large (0.35). The results in Table 6 revealed that most relationships demonstrated small to medium effect sizes, suggesting that each predictor construct contributes meaningfully to explaining variances in the endogenous variables.

Table 6: Evaluation of Path Coefficients

Hypotheses	Relationship	T value	P-value	P- value	f ²	Decision
Direct Path						
H1	Knowledge Management → Lecturer Performance	2.93	0.119	0.037	0.174	Accepted
H2	Organizational commitment	2.66	0.208	0.018	0.146	Accepted

→ Lecturer Performance						
H3	Sustainability Practices → Lecturer Performance	4.04	0.315	0.031	0.241	Accepted
H4	Work Motivation → Lecturer Performance	3.45	0.126	0.012	0.254	Accepted
H5	Job Satisfaction → Lecturer Performance	3.14	0.239	0.028	0.132	Accepted
H6	Knowledge Management → Job Satisfaction	3.24	0.326	0.016	0.172	Accepted
H7	Organizational Commitment → Job Satisfaction	3.24	0.128	0.013	0.233	Accepted
H8	Sustainability → Job Satisfaction	2.24	0.164	0.014	0.176	Accepted
H9	Work Motivation → Job Satisfaction	3.74	0.109	0.013	0.232	Accepted
Mediating path						
H1a	Knowledge Management → Job Satisfaction → Lecturer Performance	3.45	0.596	0.002	0.254	Accepted
H2b	Organizational commitment → Job Satisfaction → Lecturer Performance	3.04	0.517	0.001	0.287	Accepted
H3c	Sustainability → Job Satisfaction → Lecturer Performance	4.04	0.617	0.017	0.247	Accepted
H4d	Work Motivation → Job Satisfaction → Lecturer Performance	3.04	0.517	0.004	0.187	Accepted

This study systematically examines the interrelationship between knowledge management, organizational commitment, work motivation, sustainability practices, job satisfaction, and lecturer performances in the higher education sector in Pakistan. The empirical findings provide robust support for the proposed research framework, offering critical insights into how these constructs collectively shape lecturer performances.

The analysis presented in Table 6 demonstrates that knowledge management exerts a statistically significant positive influence on job performance ($\beta = 0.119$, $T = 2.93$, $p = 0.037$, $f^2 = 0.174$, exceeding 1.645). These results underscore that effective knowledge-sharing practice, access to

institutional knowledge resources, and organizational learning mechanisms substantially enhance faculty satisfaction, reinforcing knowledge management's value as a strategic enabler of academic performance.

The findings further reveal that organizational commitment significantly contributes to job satisfaction, with statistical evidence supporting ($\beta = 0.208$, $T = 2.66$, $p = 0.018$, $f^2 = 0.146$, exceeding 1.645). These results suggest that lecturers who feel psychological attachment, loyalty, and teaching effectiveness reinforce the importance of being a performance driver.

The results of sustainability practices also indicated a robust finding on lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.315$, $T = 4.04$, $p = 0.031$, $f^2 =$

0.241, exceeding 1.645). The findings suggest that embedding sustainability practices and social responsibility into institutional practices not only enhances environmental and social responsibility but also positively impacts classroom effectiveness and academic outcomes.

The results highlight the critical role of work motivation, showing a significant and positive relationship with lecturer performances ($\beta = 0.126$, $T = 3.45$, $p = 0.012$, $f^2 = 0.254$, exceeding 1.645). The strong statistical support suggests that motivated lecturers are more likely to demonstrate persistence, creativity, and effective teaching practices, ultimately enhancing institutional performance.

The analysis reveals that job satisfaction directly contributes to lecturer performances ($\beta = 0.239$, $T = 3.24$, $p = 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.132$, exceeding 1.645). These findings confirm that faculty members who experience higher job satisfaction are more likely to demonstrate enhanced performance, reflecting persistence, discretionary effect, and resilience in academic responsibilities.

Regarding predictors of job satisfaction, the results confirm that knowledge management strongly influences job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.326$, $T = 3.25$, $p = 0.012$, $f^2 = 0.172$, exceeding 1.645). These results highlight the pivotal role of systematic knowledge acquisition, sharing, and application in fostering a more fulfilling work environment for lecturers, boosting the sense of professional accomplishment and organizational belonging.

Similarly, the statistical evidence supports a positive relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.128$, $T = 3.24$, $p = 0.013$, $f^2 = 0.233$, exceeding 1.645). These findings affirm that effective attachment and identification with the institutions enhance lecturers' satisfaction with their roles. A committed academic workforce is more likely to remain motivated and resilient, thereby contributing to institutional stability and sustained performance.

The sustainability practices significantly positively affect job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.164$, $T = 2.24$, $p =$

0.014, $f^2 = 0.176$, exceeding 1.645). These results reflect the increasing relevance of environmentally and socially responsible practices in higher education institutions.

The work motivation also founded to positively and significantly predicted job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.109$, $T = 3.74$, $p = 0.013$, $f^2 = 0.232$, exceeding 1.645). This underscores that intrinsic and extrinsic motivational drivers, such as recognition, career advancement opportunities, and self-determination, directly enhance lecturers' satisfaction with their professional roles, thereby contributing to a thriving academic environment.

Mediating Analysis (H1a, H2b, H3c, H4d)

The mediation results provide further insights into the indirect mechanisms linking institutional and individual factors to lecturer performance via job satisfaction as a mediator. The mediation analysis indicates a significant indirect effect of knowledge management on lecturer performances through job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.596$, $T = 3.45$, $p = 0.002$, $f^2 = 0.254$, exceeding 1.645). These findings highlight that effective knowledge management enhances job satisfaction as a mediator, strengthening lecturer performances. This underscores job satisfaction as a critical pathway for organizational knowledge practices with faculty effectiveness (refer to Figure 3).

Figure 3: Mediating Analysis of Job Satisfaction

The mediation analysis of job satisfaction has confirmed a significant effect on organizational commitment and lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.517$, $T = 3.45$, $p = 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.287$, exceeding 1.645). These results indicated that higher

organizational commitment fosters greater satisfaction, elevating performance outcomes, which translate into superior performance. This meditation reinforces that commitment indirectly improves lecturer effectiveness via job satisfaction (refer to Figure 4).

Table 4: Mediating Analysis of Job Satisfaction

The analysis further reveals a robust mediation effect of job satisfaction performance ($\beta = 0.617$, $T = 4.04$, $p = 0.017$, $f^2 = 0.287$, exceeding 1.645). Adopting sustainability practices positively

contributes to job satisfaction, boosting employee performance. This emphasizes that embedding sustainability into institutional practices enhances both faculty well-being and professional outputs (refer to Figure 5).

Figure 5: Mediating Analysis of Job Satisfaction

Finally, job satisfaction also mediates the relationship between work motivation and lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.517$, $T = 3.04$, $p = 0.004$, $f^2 = 0.287$, exceeding 1.645). Motivated lecturers derive higher satisfaction from their roles, ultimately fostering improved

performances. These results confirm the crucial role of job satisfaction in channeling motivational energy into tangible academic contributions (refer to Figure 6).

Figure 6: Mediating Analysis of Job Satisfaction

Figure 7: Assessment Structural Model

Discussion of the Results

This study examined the impact of knowledge management, organizational commitment, sustainability practices, and work motivation on lecturer performance, with job satisfaction mediating variables. Anchored in the objectives, the findings extend existing literature by confirming well-established relationships and interrogating how contextual, institutional, and pedagogical factors interact in Pakistan's higher-education landscape, where lecturer turnover intention is very high and employee loyalty is still in formative stages.

The findings have confirmed that knowledge management systems play a pivotal role in enhancing lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.119$ and 0.037), confirming that institutionalized knowledge sharing and accessibility are not mere administrative enhancements but also strategic assets for academic excellence. The findings also align with the study of Abbas & Khan (2023) and Migdadi (2022), which argued that knowledge management significantly enhances lecturer performance, confirming the knowledge-based view of the firm. The results reveal that institutional leveraging of systematic knowledge-sharing platforms and tacit-explicit knowledge conversion mechanisms improve teaching, research, and service performances.

The findings have confirmed that organizational commitment also demonstrated a significant positive effect on lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.119$ and 0.037), confirming that lecturers who identify with institutional goals and share a strong emotional bond with their university demonstrate heightened discretionary effort and persistence, even in the face of resource constraints. This aligns with Patwary et al. (2025) and Purwanto (2020), highlighting that strong, effective, normative commitment employees exhibit higher discretionary effort and perseverance. Overall, the findings indicated that lecturers who feel emotionally attached and morally obliged to their institutions in higher education are more likely to perform effectively despite resource constraints.

The findings have demonstrated that sustainability practices yielded the strongest direct

predictor of lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.315$ and 0.031), confirming the most substantial direct effect on lecturer performance. Embedding sustainability into institutional culture generates a sense of shared responsibility and meaningfulness among lecturers, amplifying engagement. The findings align with the study of Amini et al. (2024) and Sepetis et al. (2020), which argued that embedding sustainability enhances employee morale, commitment, and institutional legitimacy. Overall, the finding also enhances the study's objective: lecturers' participation in sustainable practices cultivates a sense of purpose, which is positively reflected in their teaching, research, and community engagement.

Indeed, the study confirms that work motivation significantly predicted lecturers' performances ($\beta = 0.126$ and 0.012), confirming that individual motivation, loyalty, and commitment to their work can also affect organizational performance. Further, the study also aligns with the prior research of Bice et al. (2022) and Zeb et al. (2023), which posits that intrinsically motivated individuals perform better due to the drive for satisfaction from their work. These findings are mirrored in contemporary studies recognizing motivation as an essential energy for productive academic work.

Finally, the results identify that job satisfaction enhances lecturer performance ($\beta = 0.239$ and 0.028), confirming that instructors who experience higher workplace satisfaction invest more effort in teaching and research, contributing to overall institutional competitiveness. The findings of the hypothesis also align with the prior study of Al-Abdullat & Dababneh, (2018); Hendri, (2019) and Khan et al. (2019), which demonstrated that individual job satisfaction can directly affect their lecturer performance via showing the loyalty, commitment and honesty with the organization. Thus, the finding has confirmed that job satisfaction, through the teachers' commitment to the organization, can foster the lecturer's performance.

The finding of hypothesis 6 demonstrated that knowledge management also strongly affected job

satisfaction ($\beta = 0.326$ and 0.016), confirming that access to knowledge resources enhances collaboration, reduces uncertainty, and fosters a supportive environment. The study aligns with the study of (Abbas & Khan, 2023), arguing that job satisfaction promotes organizational citizenship behavior and reduces turnover intention. Thus, the findings align with the study's objective: knowledge management facilitates task efficiency and enriches the psychological climate, thereby increasing satisfaction.

The findings of hypothesis 7 indicated that organizational commitment positively influences job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.128$ and 0.013), confirming that lecturers emotionally attached to the organization demonstrated resiliencies and dedication, critical traits in an academic setting often characterized by limited resources and shifting priorities. The findings align with the studies of Gideon (2023), who found that emotional bonds foster a more fulfilling work experience, enhancing teaching quality that ultimately fosters satisfaction in the job placement. Thus, the findings are proven by the objective of the study that committed lecturers feel valued and aligned with the institutional mission, which enhances their emotional well-being and strengthens institutional loyalty.

Indeed, the findings of hypothesis 8, sustainability practices significantly influenced job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.146$ and 0.014), confirming that sustainability in institutional culture elevates employee morale and legitimacy. The study's findings align with the study of Ibarra-Cisneros et al. (2023), who indicated that lecturers engaging in environmentally and socially responsible initiatives cultivate a meaningful professional identity, aligning personal value with institutional missions. Thus, findings align with the objective that in higher education, sustainability-oriented initiatives enhance professional identity, further embedding purpose and belonging.

Last direct effect, the findings of hypothesis 9, motivation and dedication to work can significantly foster the satisfaction in their job ($\beta = 0.109$ and 0.013), confirming that intrinsic motivators are central to job satisfaction. The

findings align with the study of Aljumah (2023), which suggests that motivated lecturers derive fulfilment from academic responsibilities, strengthening their satisfaction and long-term career sustainability. Thus, the findings also confirm the study's objective that nurturing psychological needs, such as autonomy, relatedness, and sustainability initiative, creates a virtuous cycle wherein satisfaction fuels sustained academic contributions.

The mediation analysis revealed a significant indirect effect of job satisfaction on knowledge management and lecturers' performance ($\beta = 0.596$ and 0.002), indicating that knowledge management enhances performance primarily through job satisfaction. This is consistent with Habib et al. (2021); Håkansson & Johansson, (2025), who argued that satisfaction is the psychological pathway through which knowledge resources translate into effectiveness. Thus, the findings align with the objective that motivation can shape lecturers' fulfilment at work, revealing a complex interplay of organizational and personal factors in determining satisfaction outcomes.

The mediation analysis revealed a significant indirect effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment and lecturers' performance ($\beta = 0.517$ and 0.001), confirming that committed employees derive satisfaction, which in turn translates into improved performance. The findings are also aligned with the study of Purwanto (2020) and Suija-Markova (2022). A lecturer with strong organizational commitment similarly reports greater job satisfaction, supporting the argument that committed individuals perceive greater personal meaning in their role with the institutional missions. Thus, the findings demonstrate that commitment is insufficient; it must be channeled through satisfaction to drive excellence in teaching and research.

The mediation analysis showed a significant indirect effect of job satisfaction among sustainability practices and lecturers' performances ($\beta = 0.617$ and 0.017), confirming that sustainability practices further enhance job satisfaction, that responsible institutional actions

positively influence pride and intrinsic motivation, attributes that contribute to a vibrant and supportive workplace climate. In parallel with the study of Khan et al. (2019) and Roslaeni et al. (2025), a motivated lecturer reported that higher education is an inherent reward associated with academic work that fosters ongoing joy and dedication. Thus, the findings align with the study's objective to ensure that sustainability initiatives fulfil psychological needs, increase satisfaction, and improve ethical performance.

The mediation analysis showed a significant indirect effect of job satisfaction on work motivation and lecturers' performances ($\beta = 0.517$ and 0.004), confirming that motivation fuels satisfaction, which drives superior performance that enhances lecturers' performance. The findings align with (Khan et al., 2019) and Roslaeni et al. (2025), emphasizing the role of intrinsic motivation in fostering creativity, persistence, and productivity in knowledge-intensive professions. Thus, satisfaction serves as the psychological engine that transforms motivational energy into academic contributions.

Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the interplay between knowledge management, organizational commitment, sustainability practices, work motivation, and job satisfaction in shaping lecturer performance within higher education institutions in Pakistan. This dual role underscores that job satisfaction is a crucial mediator, translating organizational and individual factors into improved teaching and overall faculty effectiveness. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating strategies that foster a supportive knowledge environment, institutional loyalty, and higher education institutions. These can boost lecturers' productivity and sustainability, ultimately advancing academic excellence and institutional competitiveness.

Theoretical and Practical Contributions

The study advances theory by empirically demonstrating that job satisfaction is a direct

driver of lecturer performance and a mediating mechanism linking knowledge management, organizational commitment, sustainability practices, and work motivation to performance outcomes. This is done by integrating these constructs into a unified model. The study enriches the literature on academic performance by highlighting the interplay between institutional practices and individual psychology. Moreover, the validated mediating role of job satisfaction extends organizational behavior and higher education strategies influence lecturer effectiveness.

Practically, these findings underscore the necessity of university administrators and policymakers to prioritize strategies that enhance job satisfaction, as it magnifies the impact of organizational and motivational factors on performance. Institutions should invest in a robust knowledge-sharing system and foster supportive incentive structures that motivate lecturers. By embedding these strategies into higher education policies, universities can enhance lecturer productivity, ensure institutional sustainability, and align with the goals of educational excellence and competitiveness.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

Despite the valuable contribution, the study has several limitations that warrant attention. First, the data were collected from a single regional context, which may limit the generalizability of the findings across different cultural and institutional environments. Future research could employ cross-region comparisons or multi-institutional datasets to enhance the study's external validation. Second, the reliance on self-reported survey responses introduces common method bias. Subsequent studies should consider mixed-methods approaches, incorporating qualitative interviews and longitudinal design to capture more dynamic insights. Third, while job satisfaction was established as a key mediator, other operational mediating or moderating factors, such as leadership style, institutional policies, or digital transformation initiatives, were not examined. Future studies could extend the

model by integrating these variables to provide a more comprehensive understanding of lecturer performance. Lastly, the study's cross-sectional design restricts causal inference; longitudinal or experimental approaches are recommended to establish stronger causal relationships among knowledge management, organizational commitment, sustainability practices, work motivation, and lecturer outcomes.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest in the work reported in this paper.

Funding: this research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or non-profit sectors

Authors' Contributions: GM: conceptualization, methodology, data collection, data analysis, writing, original draft; literature review, write-review and editing, visualization; supervision, validation, project administration, writing-review & editing; visualization, investigation, resources, funding acquisition. Additionally, all authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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